

CHANGES OF RUSSIAN LANGUAGE TEXTBOOKS IN CHINESE EDUCATION SYSTEM: A CASE OF RUSSIAN LANGUAGE MAJOR IN A CHINESE NORMAL UNIVERSITY

Sesegma Balzhirova¹

School of Education, Northeast Normal University,
5268 Renmin Street, Changchun 130024, China

Abstract:

This study examines Russian Language Textbooks (RLT) published in China since 1949 to uncover the changes that have happened to the Status of Russian Language Education in China in various historical periods since 1949. The study explores the major differences throughout these historical periods regarding Russian Language Education in Chinese Normal Universities and the factors have contributed to these changes. The study has examined the changes of Russian language textbooks in different Chinese political, economic, social and cultural contexts and found a tendency of the textbooks to move from collectivist ideologies, serving mainly the interests of the country in the 1950s to individualist ideologies that concern the interests of the learners in the 2000s. In addition, the learners for whom the textbooks were designed were being socialized into the identity of Chinese citizens (socialist patriots) in the 1950s but global citizens in the 2000s. The functions of Russian language in China, in turn, shifted during this time from facilitating communication for scientific, business and travelling purposes, to enhancing cross-cultural understanding in the 21st century. The study was concluded with a discussion of the implications of the research on textbooks for Russian language education.

Keywords: Russian Language Textbook (RLT), ideology, Normal University

1. Introduction

The China-Russia Brotherhood, which lasted from 1921 to 1959, was followed by a period of hostility, between 1960 to 1988, which was then moderated into the present day relationship. The relationship between the two countries had actually been between the Soviet Communist Party (CCCP) and the Chinese Communist Party (CPC). It dates back to 1921 when CPC was founded. After World War II, the whole world was divided into two groups: that of the Capitalist Group and the Socialist Group. After the

¹ Correspondence: email sesegmabalzhirova@yandex.ru

founding of the People's Republic of China, CPC decided China should be a socialist country. CPC wanted to emulate the USSR example. Therefore, had to rely on USSR for support and guidance. China's policy-making was greatly influenced by USSR. The CPC and government sent many leaders and intellectuals to USSR to learn from their counterparts in Russia. In order to learn from the USSR, people needed to master the Russian language. The only way to achieve this was teach Russian in schools. Russian became the most widely taught foreign language in schools. Russian was promoted at the expense of English because of China's political alliance and economic construction

1.1 Statement of the problem

In recent years, China has included Russian as a foreign language in national curriculum. Russian is taught in colleges and universities as well as in some high schools. Chinese culture is or will be enriched again with the re-introduction of Russian language and her culture. Therefore, it seems necessary to understand reasons for re-introducing Russian from historical, political, economic and pedagogical perspectives. The learning of Russian is a crucial aspect of China's opening up to the world and its increasing prominent global role. The contention of this study is that there has been a gap in the current Russian language textbooks. Textbooks are a primary tool for the socialization of students into particular identities, stances, communities, and language practices worldwide. Therefore, it is essential that these materials be examined closely for their underlying messages.

1.2 Research objectives

Based on the purpose above, the study was guided by the following objectives;

1. To examine the changes of Russian language textbooks in Chinese normal universities since 1949
2. To investigate how the Russian language textbooks in Chinese education have been used.
3. To find out the factors for the changes in Russian language textbooks in China.

1.3 Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What changes have happened to the Russian Language Textbooks in China since 1949?
2. How to understand these changes from the teachers' perspective?
3. What factors contributed to these changes?

2. Significance of the study

The findings will contribute to the applied linguistics regarding the changes of a foreign language textbook throughout social, political and economic contexts.

The knowledge generated from this study is expected to;

1. Create awareness to the government and teacher educators on the importance of Russian language education.
2. Provide knowledge on how to establish effective Russian language textbooks to teacher educators.
3. Provide guidelines on teaching of Russian language education in Chinese Universities on the practicability of the Russian textbooks.

3. Analytical framework

The study is going to examine changes in Russian Language Textbooks use in the Chinese Education System from three aspects namely Publisher of Textbook, Prime Concentration and Ideologies and Methodologies in the four periods ranging from Before the Cultural Revolution (1950 to 1964), During the Cultural Revolution (1966 to 1978), After the Cultural Revolution (1980 to 1989) and from 1990 to the present through documentary analysis technique as shown in Figure 1.

Period	Publisher of textbook	Prime concentration & ideologies	Methodologies
Before cultural revolution (1950-1964)	Mostly produced in Russia & People's Education Press (PEP)	Stress on USSR'S Kairov's pedagogy on audiolingualism	Teacher-centered, focus on accuracy and written language memorization
During cultural revolution (1966-1978)	Ministry of Education of PRC produced & PEP	Stagnation, political propaganda	Teacher centered, focus on accuracy and written language
After cultural revolution (1980-1989)	Jointly published by Western publishers, MOE & PEP	Focus on functional / national approach	Oral Practice in contextualized situations, memorization, student independent learning, accuracy in written language
1990 – present days	Produced by Ministry of Education & PEP	Task Based learning	Oral and written practice in contextualized situations

Figure 1: Analytical framework

3.1 Research Methodology

The study employed a Qualitative Research Design. The qualitative research design is adopted in order to gain a deep and comprehensive understanding of the personal experiences of Russian Language Teachers. This approach is considered appropriate for the study because the study is not concerned with measurement but with exploring teachers' personal experiences and their views about the Russian Language Textbooks in relation to the changes which had taken place. It will involve a comparative analysis of Textbooks in various periods of time, from 1950s.

In this research, interviews were used to gather information from different libraries such as Northeast Normal University (NENU), Heilongjiang University and Harbin Normal University in order to show comparatively a documentary analysis of Russian language textbooks and teacher educators' views on the use of Russian Language Textbooks.

3.2 Study Area

The study was conducted in the department of Russian language within the three Normal Universities: Northeast Normal University, Heilongjiang University and Harbin Normal University, all in the Northeast of China. The researcher conducted the study only with five teachers; among them, four were Chinese and one Russian. Of the four Chinese teachers, three teachers were from NENU while the other one was from Heilongjiang University located in Harbin. The Russian teacher was teaching at NENU. The reason for their selection was based on the accessibility of data at NENU.

3.3 Sampling

This study employed a non-probability sampling technique to draw its sample. Specifically, a total population purposive sampling technique was used. Since the study had only two areas for collecting data and respondents who shared similar characteristics were few, the use of purposive sampling was convenient. All Russian language teachers were identified in all the Departments of Russian Language within the three Normal Universities (NENU, Heilongjiang and Harbin). Therefore, the total sample size selected was five teachers. A population of 40 textbooks on Russian language teaching was identified. The books originated from 1950 to the present. The period of study was broken into four sections –before Cultural Revolution, During the Cultural Revolution, After the Cultural Revolution and from the 1990s to the Present (2014). Purposively, two books from each of the four periods were purposively sampled. According to Patlot (1990), as cited in Israel (2012), a total population is a type of purposive sampling technique where the researcher chooses to examine the entire population having similar characteristics in such a way that if a small population will be excluded in the study a significant piece of information will be missing. Based on this fact, the researcher collected data from all teachers who had work experience of 10-15 years and above. The choice was based on the fact that one year experience is enough for a teacher to learn and understand using Russian Language textbooks. Interviews were held with the five teachers.

3.4 Instruments of data collection

Based on the fact that the study employed a qualitative research design, documentary analysis technique and interview guides were the main instruments for data collection. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with the teachers of Russian language. The use of variety of methods for data collection enabled the researcher to collect reliable data.

3.5 Interviews

An interview can simply be defined as a conversation with a purpose of gathering information (Berg, 2001). In order to find the perspective of teachers and extract the knowledge from them, semi-structured interviews were conducted. The interviewees were five teachers. The interview questions focused on the developmental changes that have been occurring in the designing and content of Russian language textbooks and the factors behind the changes in them on the given span of time. The principals were also asked to share their views on the latest trends and the methodologies they have been adopting according to their own experiences. The interviews were recorded along with important points being noted and sent through mail for analysis. Further to that, the recorded interviews were also sent to the respective teachers for further confirmation in case they wanted to add or skip something.

3.6 Validity and reliability of Instrument of Data Collection

Validity intends to look at whether the research measures what is intended to be measured. This means, the extent to which results can be interpreted accurately and can be generalized to the population, situations and conditions (Wiersma & Jurs 2004). To ensure validity, the interviews used featured enough points of discussion focusing on the objectives of the study. Since validity ensures that data collected through the interview can yield the same results, the points and comments shared during interviews, the recorded interviews and outlines were sent back to the teachers for validation. According to Basit (2010), reliability intends to know the repeatability of results to similar study conducted by using the same participants and context. For this purpose, the Research Supervisor was constantly involved fully during the Interview construction process in order to ensure accurate, reliable and valid data were collected.

4. Findings and Discussions

The researcher managed to find and analyze the 40 textbooks and manuals on the Russian language, created and published at different times in China. The number of analyzed textbooks publication year is distributed as follows: 10 textbooks (1950 to 1964); 2 textbooks (1966 to 1978); 12 textbooks (1980 to 1989); 16 textbooks from 1990 to the present day. In addition, the researcher seek to uncover the main changes of Russian textbooks and the major differences throughout these historical periods of the textbooks, seemingly intended by the textbook writers for teachers to use and explore their connections with the context in which they were produced. Furthermore, the researcher briefly discuss the interrelationship of the various agencies involved in the production of textbooks in China and how it has changed over the past decades and which factors contributed to these changes.

As shown in Table 1: Description of Russian Language Textbooks, Russian Language Textbooks in China have passed from a those promoting socialist and

communist ideologies to those promoting friendliness, communication and international business among the two countries.

Table 1: Description of Russian Language Textbooks

Time	Title	Level	Publisher	Important Facts
Before Cultural revolution (1950-1964)	Russian Language or Grammar of Russian Language	Institutions of Russian language and Faculty of Russian language	PEP and Russian publishers	1. This series was the most widely used Russian textbook series in the history of Russian language education in China.
During Cultural revolution (1966- 1978)	Elementary course of Russian Language	Institutions of Russian language (1 st grade)	PEP	1. This series served as the cornerstone of late-20 th century Russian education in China as it was published right after the announcement of China's Open Door Policy in 1978. 2. This series was also the only Russian language Textbook series used in China at that time.
After Cultural revolution (1980- 1989)	Basic Russian language course for students	Institutions of Russian language and Faculty of Russian language	PEP and jointly produced by Western publishers	2. This series covers over 80% of the areas in China (Adamson, 1997). It is also the first set of textbooks after the implementation of "One Curriculum, Multiple Textbooks" policy.
1990 - present day	Russian language textbook for Chinese students philologists majoring in Russian language	Chinese Normal Universities	PEP and Russian publishers	This series is the latest Russian language textbook series for Normal Universities students published by PEP.

While Russians are losing interest in their culture of speech, the Russian language has been gaining popularity in China, no matter how strange it may sound. The knowledge of the English language is considered very prestigious in Russia. If a Russian is fluent in English, he or she may consider themselves professionally successful. In China, students rush for special courses to study Russian. The interest in the Russian language has been growing steadily in China recently. It is incredibly hard for a Chinese national to learn how to speak Russian. It is just as hard, as it is for a Russian to learn how to speak Chinese. However, Russian is becoming more and more important in China

because the nation's political and economic cooperation with Russia continues to expand every year.

4.1 Changes in the Russian Language Textbooks in China Since 1949

Russian language is the state language of the Russian Federation, as well as one of the official languages of the United Nations, China officially recognized Russian as one of the languages of China's ethnic minorities. Teaching Russian in China first began in the 1708's roughly 150 years earlier than learning of other European languages. Since then it has been over 300 years (Fu Ke, 1986)

Russian language serves as a means of international communication in politics, economy, culture, diplomacy, etc. Russian language has played an important role in the history of the development of relations between China and Russia. In the last decade in many provinces, cities, and especially in the city of Heihe with its unique geographical position came to the fore teaching Russian as a foreign language. (Gu JiaQi, 2011).

According to the words of Sun Chao, the teacher at the Heilongjiang University:

"Not by chance in China "great and mighty" began to study at the state level in Harbin - Chinese city with a tragic Slavic fate. It was founded in 1898 by Russians who came to build the CER. During the heyday of Harbin lived more than two hundred thousand Russian citizens. The mass exodus of our people began after transfer under Chinese jurisdiction CER in the late 30 years of last century. Rusists of Harbin admit that the hardest thing they had, not counting the cultural- revolutionary years in the mid-90s . Russia did not like itself, all its Soviet past with dumped ship today. Under the rubble of empire around the world have been and the Department of Slavic Studies. Previously, from 1950 to 1970 interest in the Russian language was, but not to such a great extent as now. I think that the interest in Russian language increases especially in the north of China. What is the reason given the increasing interest in the Russian language, the fact that Russia and China since ancient times are neighboring countries and the connection between us, not only in politics but also in economy, trade, education and culture".

Olga, the Professor of the Russian language from Northeast Normal University shared her own opinion about the status of the Russian Language education in China thus:

"In China, the interest in the Russian language is becoming popular, and the English language is reduced. This year, Ministry of education in Beijing decided to reduce the number of points for admission to universities. Previously, for admission to the specialty «English language " needed to score 150 points, but by 2016, went lower to 100 points. As the students devote much time to the study of English at admission, it is reflected on the study of the native language. For example, in southern China won't impose an English exam".

"I can also add that earlier when we talked about the teaching of the Russian language in our university, few people knew that it taught here. Now, many people know that the Russian language is taught and popularized not only in our university, but in others too. There are many diverse cultural and social events holding and indicating the relevance of studying Russian language in China".

The respondents' views just underscore the fact that the increasing interest in the Russian language emanates from the historic and neighbourly links between Russia and China since ancient times as well as the connection between them, not only in politics but also in economy, trade, education and culture.

4.2 Understanding the Changes in Russian Language Textbooks use from the teachers Perspective

Over the past 50 years in China published 7 training programs in Russian language for secondary schools and universities. In the preceding period on teaching Russian language influenced the techniques used technique Soviet Russian as a foreign language (RCTs) dominated the study of grammar, translation and more. These methodological procedures laid a solid foundation of knowledge of students, but often converted language not into a living language as a means of communication, but converted only into in a dry scheme. Particular attention was paid to grammar, but remained aloof live speech, as a result of Chinese students remembered well the individual words, know the rules of grammar but could not communicate freely with Russian in different communicative situations. (Lu Yunhun, 2009)

Also according to the words of Sun Chao, the teacher at the Heilongjiang University:

"As for textbooks, there are five university publishing Russian textbooks. They are Beijing, Shanghai, Harbin, Heilongjiang and Luoyang universities. The Last one it is Military School on preparation of experts of foreign languages. Every five or six years publishers produced new textbooks as a textbook materials do not go over time. Content of textbooks is old and therefore they should be changed. For example, in Heilongjiang University we are using new textbooks studying pedagogy of teaching foreign languages, publishing in Beijing. Old and new textbooks have advantages and disadvantages. For example, students who attend four years from textbooks are not so fluent in Russian, since it is impossible to include all common words. We can say that in these textbooks used "pure literary language", but you use more simple words routine life".

As for changes in Russian textbooks, teacher Sun Chao said these changes can be presented by advantages between old and new manuals:

"Advantages of the new textbooks that they are new materials. For example, there are materials directly from the internet. I believe that the old textbooks better, as there are

classic works of famous writers, but now they cannot find in textbooks or find, but they are few. Previously drawn attention to the theory of the Russian language, such as grammar, and now pays more attention to speaking. I started to teach in 1996 and I can say that from my point of view, students do not try so hard as before. Since this time is the century of advanced media tools such as the Internet, electronic dictionaries, TB, all these facilitate learning and students are not forced to work in full force if to compare with previous years, for example, when we were studying in the 60s, 70s . Another important factor is that now we have university teachers who are native Russian speakers, but before we didn't have. Of course it is good and therefore it is necessary to increase the number of teachers, native speakers."

Irina, Deputy Dean at the Faculty of Russian language and Russian language teacher shared her opinion about understanding of changes to Russian Language textbooks in Chinese Normal Universities from teacher`s prospective:

"In the past years, the content of textbooks was influence by pressing policy namely the ideology of communism and socialism. And now of course we have more freedom. It all depends on the demands of the people. We produced textbooks for students so that they can quickly master in the Russian language and we pay attention to the materials that are needed in the first place. For example, common words, rather than political terms. When I was a student, we had in textbooks such political terms as "the proletariat" and there were so many, and now no longer exists. In modern textbooks of Russian language used more modern lexicology as we go with the times, and of course content, methods and structure of the textbooks are changing".

The interviewees affirm the fact that the methodology and content had changed since 1949 to the present time. In the beginning, it was full of political terms and propaganda, ideologies of communism and socialism but now ideologies of new textbooks are about travelling, diplomacy, learning culture while the concentration is on speaking not grammar as before. That is why students have communicative problems due to lack of grammar in their foundations.

In recent years, there has been the number of students who want to learn Russian as a foreign language in favor of English. Among the main reasons, the following may be mentioned: *firstly*, the extension function of English language in the world due to globalization; *Secondly*, fast obsolescence and failure to update the content and methodological support, accompanying learning Russian, current phenomenon that can be seen as a problem from many aspects, considering the factors that led to the status of Russian language in the border China.

4.3 Cross Border Relations

In recent years, trade relations with Russia have been on decline in Heihe, despite the advantage of geographical location and rich natural the possibility of cross-border

region. Trade with other countries began to supplant trade with Russia with the prospect of external trade and the province of Heihe Heilongjiang with other countries. Naturally began to decrease the need for people who are able to conduct communication in Russian. People studying Russian language do not feel the prospects of its development in this direction, and the desire to learn Russian language begins to plummet. (Gu JiaQi, 2011).

4.4 The era of computerization

The development of emergency information received and computer technology, they become generally available. This process also contributed to the decline in the prestige of the Russian language in China, particularly in the border, as the area of the Russian language in the global information space is quite narrow. It turns out that in the years of rapid and dramatic growth of information, years of development and implementation of computer information technology to study Russian language becomes unprofitable. In addition, Chinese students studying Russian language note the difficulties of perception in Russian Internet communications. Students, who are taught Russian language, complain that during use computer technology in the classroom, they have difficulty: un separated look screen, but do not understand. Thus, the lack of demand for Russian language in the era of general information and computerization also leads to a drop in the number of Russian learners.

4.5 Russian language in Chinese universities

During enrollment at some universities, there are restrictions on exam in a foreign language, and it is observed even when recruiting graduate: some universities do not accept examinees on Russian as a foreign language. In April 2001, the Ministry of Education of China indicated that while university admissions should not be restricted set, requiring entering the exam results at any particular foreign language. But in the same 2001 in a number of universities in China were restrictions have passed state exams in a foreign language, in particular Russian language. This reduced activity of Russian language teachers and students, Russian learners. To go to a good university, strong in the Russian language students have to learn another foreign language. This not only resulted in that students have spent time researching the subject is not suitable for go to college, but many talented students were thrown halfway in the study their chosen foreign language - Russian. This also leads to the fact that studying Russian language becomes less and less. (He Hongmei, 2004).

4.6 The content of new Russian textbooks

The necessary negative factor called that training manuals of Russian as a foreign language are currently in use in China, are essentially obsolete. The contents will not correspond to the present state of affairs in Russian society. Now the lessons of Russian language in high and middle schools using textbooks that were issued Higher Education Publishing House in 2000. In universities often use manual "Basic Russian

language course in universities, "which Publishing House of Higher Education released in 1998 (only 4 parts) [3]. Many texts these benefits are in isolation from the modern environment. Their content is general, non-specific, as suggested by most of the exercises are designed on rote memorization. The manual does not satisfy the needs of students in acquisition of speech and communication skills relevant to the modern areas life, while the proposed content in textbooks is divorced from reality and most of the information presented there, used in the practice of communication is very rare, and the result of this in the end is that can be defined the phrase "dumb Russian language." In this sense, teaching Russian as a foreign language in China is far from new communicative concept of foreign language teaching in general and those innovative ideas in the teaching of foreign languages, which are actively promoted in China now. (Tong Tsang, 2000).

4.7 The status of Russian language

Many schools do not pay due attention to training Russian language: not all schools have teachers of the Russian language, neither do they have language laboratories for teaching Russian language nor multimedia classrooms. They also lack teaching materials and reference books in sufficient quantity for student – self work etc. It gives students, who are studying Russian language, a feeling of rejection and certainly dampens activity in the study of the Russian language as in both instructors and students. Is difficult in such conditions to lead effective training, students are passive pursuits. Due to insufficient active forms a situation passive learning, the learning resulting in a decrease interest, curiosity. Furthermore, possible limitations in perspective enroll in college; it is associated with the examination in Russian as a foreign language also lead to a decrease of students (He Hongmei, p.136 -137, 2004).

However, in recent years the Russian language teaching in Normal Universities had some problems, among which are the following.

1. Problem of the enrollment

There is tendency in some secondary schools to stop teaching Russian as a foreign language, for example, in the city of Heihe (He Hongmei, 2004). So number of students of Russian language each year will decline. Furthermore, the quality teaching is also getting worse, probably due to inconsistencies objective modern requirements for foreign language teaching. This state of affairs certainly will effect on the development of Russian language study in high school. As soon as the scope of English becoming wider and wider, the number of those who study Russian language in order to enter into school and then go abroad, etc., and gradually decreases move from the interior to the border area of the city to the village. Due to the fact that it was not possible to study Russian in school, most Russian students in the faculties of language begin to learn the Russian language from scratch. It significantly affects the quality of teaching gifted students who studied Russian language to university. Learn Russian language in high school in the state in which it now is of concern to parents and the public.

2. *Lack of teachers*

Number of young teachers and middle-aged predominates, but despite the fact that they have a higher degree, they are found as inferior teachers on their knowledge, skills and experience. In addition, few teachers internships abroad. Consequently, they are insufficiently aware of the culture and the actual realities of modern Russia. In the classroom at such teachers, lack a living relationship to the subject of teaching, and the status of these teachers inevitably reduced. In some universities, the teaching staff Russian language is not staffed: no permanent teachers of the Russian language, for teaching invited professors from other universities. Experienced teachers are sorely lacking.

3. *Problem techniques and methodology of teaching Russian as foreign language*

Note the following aspects of this problem. First, teachers of Russian language in the universities do not have sufficient knowledge about the laws of functioning linguistic system and the Russian language in particular. They are often unaware of that features of the language system and changes in grammar and vocabulary are largely due to features of contemporary culture and the political situation. The basis of language learning should be basic knowledge of the language and the laws of the features of its operation. Teacher of the Russian language, as well as any other teacher language, you cannot have a simplified representation of the language and take it only as means for transmitting external information. In order to prepare good speaking language students need to familiarize them with the theoretical information about the Russian language, prevailing in Russian linguistics. Second, teachers of the Russian language by objective and subjective reasons are reduced learning objectives. some teachers believe that the main and sometimes the only goal of employment in the Russian language - prepare students to read and understand texts in Russian, and the formation abilities to listen, speak, write, translate - it does not matter. Teachers, of course, interested in the most positive result of their students on the exam, therefore primarily organize the work of students on the development of a variety of analog examination topics, try to develop the habit of thinking necessary for passing examinations. Thirdly, there is a clear mismatch between a small number of hours devoted to training on a foreign (Russian) language, and a large amount of information provided for the development, which also negative impact on the quality of teaching Russian as a foreign language.

4. *Problem of curriculum for students majoring in "Russian language", and the quality of their implementation.*

This problem concerns mainly teaching Russian students studying Russian as a foreign language, and not receiving specialty related to the Russian language as the scope of future professional activity - the so -called "not specialized" students. In universities, classes in Russian language only held on the first and second years, and after exams in Russian language training ends. Thus after closure Institute students mastered vocabulary is greatly reduced, and the ability

to verbally speech is markedly reduced. In addition, the implementation of the curriculum in the specialty "Russian language" use of equipment multimedia learning is not developed in sufficiently meets the requirements of modern educational process (as for example, when teaching English), very few sources of media learning. Deficiencies in a number of hours on Russian lessons leads to that the teacher has time to perform only basic learning objectives , and time is to lead a diverse educational activities on the subject, is not enough. Rational component dominates the teaching that leads to reduced interest in students in language learning and provides the highest possible result of training. The situation must, in our view, change .In order to justify the choice for these textbooks, we have illustrated in this chapter the unique social, cultural and political context in which each of textbooks was produced and how such particular context contributed to varying ideologies embedded in the textbooks.

In addition, we have discussed how the construction of the textbooks and the pedagogical approach adopted by each textbook transitioned over the past decades and how it signified an increasingly relaxed and open mentality of the Chinese government in the recent years; yet, the transition also revealed the power that the government remained to hold as it continued to integrate into the international market.

5. Conclusions

The main focus of the study was the changes of Russian language textbooks in Chinese education: Study of Russian Language Major in a Chinese Normal University through documentary analysis and interviews which was then broken down to three research questions:

The study was conducted to answer the following research questions;

1. What changes have happened to the Russian Language Textbooks in China since 1949?
2. How to understand these changes from the teachers` perspective?
3. What factors contributed to these changes?

Using data from the textbooks, study approached the questions primarily by investigating the use of Russian language textbooks in China since various historical periods since 1949. (1) What changes have happened to the Russian Language textbooks in China since 1949; and what and how ideologies were woven into textbooks through the above means? Background information regarding text use and classroom interaction contributed to a better understanding of the changes of the ideologies reflected in the content of the textbooks. It was observed that most textbooks today represent the results of the negotiation and interplay amongst the CPC, educational policy, the market and the textbook users. Collaboration in the production of Russian language textbooks between PEP and Russian publishers such as "Vostok" and "The Pushkin State Russian Language Institute" was observed. Since 1980 years, foreign agencies were involved in the writing of the textbooks but before they were not. Involvement of

the Foreign Agencies in the writing of the textbooks showed increased relaxed mentality of the Chinese government towards the subject matter of the books. (2) How to understand these changes from the teacher's prospective: China published Seven training programs in Russian language for secondary schools and universities in the past 50 years. The teaching of Russian language was influenced by the Soviet Russian language techniques and pedagogy which dominated the study of grammar, translation and more. Methodological procedures laid a solid foundation of knowledge among students. Particular attention was paid to grammar and (3) What factors contributed to these changes? Traces of a rising China, which stressed the changing face of its economy in the global community (Duff et al., 2013), were consistently identified in these textbooks.

The learners were socialized into an identity that saw themselves as the host of the country responsible for welcoming and accommodating foreign visitors and into textbooks of helpful and cordial behaviors that would make the stay of the foreigners more pleasant, and thus, would further create a foreigner-friendly environment in real life. Such a representation of the country underlines the increasingly connected relationship between China and the world. The functions of Russian transformed from being used to assist scientific exchange to aid overseas travelling and business around the world.

Generally speaking, the structural elements evolved from being used to communicate collectivist (what we need to do as a country) ideologies, state patriotism in the 1950s to more individualist ideologies (what you need to do as an individual) in the early 2000s.

In the following section, the researcher discuss how the readers of the textbooks were socialized into a particular perspective of China, the world, the identities of the learners and the functions of Russian that help to maintain dominance and social reproduction.

Before Cultural Revolution (1950- 1964) and during Cultural Revolution (1966-1978) recognize an intention of the Chinese government to socialize students into a perspective that saw itself as a strong power in the world and a changed state from its past. A grave and poignant life before the Communist Party came into power was compared with the comfortable and happy life people enjoyed afterward. Apart from that, personal recount as another strategy was deployed to paint the picture of the past in order to reinforce the idea of transformation of the state (e.g., a senior scientist shared his life in the past where he was deprived of education opportunities and had to work for the rich at a young age).

After Cultural Revolution and from the 1990, the idea of a strong and changed China was downplayed as the country proceeded to its 17th year of opening up to the world. The socialization of such ideologies became more subtle and implicit. For instance, the significance of the Chinese language regarding its number of speakers in the world to indirectly point to the idea of China being a powerful country; yet, none was discovered to explicitly promote the image of the country. At the same time, the

image of a rising and friendly China became more salient. Such a construction can be interpreted partially as a reflection of China's growing economy in the 1990s and its softened foreign policies in dealing with international issues (e.g., "good-neighbour" diplomacy). It can also be seen as a strategy to socialize the young generation into a certain version of understanding about the country and its place in the world that assist the social reproduction of dominance (e.g., the learners would hold a friendly attitude to the foreign visitors who often come to travel or to seek investment opportunities in China in the 1990s).

By 2003, China had furthered its integration into the global community, particularly in the economic and cultural realm (e.g., accession into the WTO in 2001; Beijing's successful bid for the 2008 Olympic Games in 2001). Such a relationship was reflected in the new textbooks from 1990 till present day, where the country was positioned as an integral part of the world; however, not a superior part.

Regarding the functions of Russian, the instrumental approach seemed to have shifted to a more humanitarian approach in the sense that Russian language was meant largely to facilitate cross-cultural communication and to enhance one's understanding about the diverse cultures associated with the Russian language. Furthermore, we also see a transition in the emphasis and function of Russian language textbooks from being used explicitly as a source for both language teaching and Chinese citizenship education in 1950 (e.g., politics and sociology in China) to being used implicitly for Chinese citizenship education but more explicitly as a resource for foreign language instruction and global citizenship and inter culturalism in 2003.

References

1. Apple, M. W. (1990). *Ideology and curriculum*. New York: Routledge. Apple, M. W., & Christian-Smith, L. K. (1991). *The politics of the textbook*. New York: Routledge.
2. Bourdieu, P. 1991. *Language and Symbolic Power*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
3. Coulmas, F., ed. 1997. *The Handbook of Sociolinguistics*. Oxford: Blackwell.
4. Crystal D. 1997. *The Cambridge Encyclopedia of Language*. 2nd ed. Cambridge & New York: Cambridge University Press.
5. Crystal, D. (1997). *English as a global language*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
6. Cramsch, C. (1991), *Context and Culture in Language Teaching*. Oxford University Press.
7. Curran, C.A. (1976), *Counselling-Learning in Second Languages*, Apple River, Illinois: Apple River Press.
8. CNNIC (China Internet Network Information Center). (2011). *The 2010 Research Report of the Development of the Internet Network in the Countryside of China*.

- Retrieved from <http://www.cnnic.net.cn/research/bgxz/ncbg/201109/P020110906360062661430.pdf> [In Chinese.]
9. Chan, L-H., Chan, G., & Kwan, F.. (2011). *China at 60: Global-local interactions*. Hackensack, N.J: World Scientific. CTMRI [Curriculum and Teaching Materials Research Institute]. (2001). *Ershi shiji zhongguo zhongxiaoxue kecheng biao zhun jiaoxue dagang huibian: waiguoyu juan yingyu*. [A compilation of primary and secondary English syllabuses in the 20th century.] Beijing: People's Education Press. [In Chinese.]
 10. Deng, X. P. (1977), (1978) and (1979). *Selections from Deng Xiaoping: 1975-1982*. Beijing: People's Education Press.
 11. Dittmer, L. & Chen, R. (1981), *Ethics and Rhetoric of the Chinese Cultural Revolution*, Studies in Chinese Terminology No. 19, Berkeley: Centre for Chinese Studies, University of California.
 12. Dittmer, L. (1987), *China's Continuous Revolution: the Post-Liberation Epoch 1949-81*. Berkely: University of California Press.
 13. Eagleton, T. (1991). *Ideology: An introduction*. New York: Verso.
 14. Fu, K. (1986) *History of foreign language teaching in China*. Shanghai: Shanghai Foreign Language Education Press. [In Chinese.]
 15. Hogan, T. (1996). *Globalization: Experiences and explanations*. In A. Kellehear (Ed.), *Social Self, Global Culture*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
 16. Hu, W. Z. (In Press). *A matter of balance: Reflections on China's language policy in education*. The Third International Symposium on ELT, Beijing China: Foreign Language Teaching and Research Press.
 17. Hill, P. 2003. *Language and national identity*. In Liddicoat, A., & Muller, K. (eds), *Perspective on Europe: Language Issues and Language Planning in Europe*, (Melbourne: Language Australia) 11-20.
 18. Ingram, D. 1977a. *Language teaching in the pluralist society – The challenge for teacher educators*. *Babel*, 13:1, 9-18.
 19. Fairclough, N. 1989. *Language and Power*. London & New York: Longman.
 20. Kanno, Y., & Norton, B. (2003). *Imagined communities and educational possibilities: Introduction*. *Journal of Language, Identity, and Education*, 2(4), 241-249.
 21. Kress, G. R., & Hodge, B. (1979). *Language as ideology*. London: Routledge & Kegan Paul.
 22. Kubota, R. (2011). *Questioning linguistic instrumentalism: English, neoliberalism, and language tests in Japan*. *Linguistics and Education*, 22(3), 248-260.
 23. Lam, A. (2002). *English in education in China: Policy changes and learners' experiences*. *World Englishes*, 21(2), 245-256.
 24. Lakoff, R. T. (2000). *The Language War*. Berkeley: University of California Press.

25. Lee, D. (2010). Portrayals of non-North Koreans in North Korean textbooks and the formation of national identity. *Asian Studies Review*, 34(3), 349-369.
26. Lisovskaya, E., & Karpov, V. (1999). New ideologies in post-Communist Russian textbooks. *Comparative Education Review*, 43(4), 522-543.
27. Liu Guangzhun. *Guanyu Zhongguo Eyu Jiaoxue Qingkuang de Diaocha Baogao*. – Beijing, 2004. (Лю Гуанчжунь. Доклад о положении обучения русскому языку в Китае. – Пекин, 2004.) Доклад Министерства иностранных дел Российской Федерации «Русский язык в мире». – Москва, 2003.
28. Liu Yonghong. *Huidanglingjueding – Lun Woguo Eyu Rencai Suzhi Peiyang de JIGE Guanxi // Zhongguo Eyu Jiaoxue*. – 2000. – No.4. (Лю Юнхун. О проблеме подготовки высококвалифицированного персонала по специальности русский язык // Русский язык в Китае. – 2000. – №4.)
29. Liu, Y. B. (2005). Discourse, cultural knowledge and ideology: a critical analysis of Chinese language textbooks. *Pedagogy, Culture and Society*, 13(2), 233-264.
30. Luke, A. (1988). *Literacy, textbooks, and ideology: Postwar literacy instruction and the mythology of Dick and Jane*. New York: Falmer Press. Ministry of Education (2001b). *Guiding Ideas to Improve the Quality of Undergraduate Teaching (guanyu jiaoqiang gaodeng xuexiao benke jiaoxue gongzuo tigio jiaoxue zhiliangde ruogan yijian)* (Document No. 4). Beijing: Ministry of Education. [In Chinese]
31. Mao, Z. D. (1949). *On people's dictatorship*. In *Selections from Mao Zedong* (1991 ed.). Beijing: People's Education Press.
32. Norton, B. & Toohey, K. (2011). Identity, language learning, and social change. *Language Teaching*, 44(4), 412-446.
33. Norton, B. (2000). *Identity and language learning: Gender, ethnicity and educational change*. Harlow, UK: Pearson Education/Longman.
34. Norton Peirce, B. (1995). Social identity, investment, and language learning. *TESOL Quarterly*, 29(1), 9–31.
35. Nozaki, Y., Openshaw, R., & Luke, A. (Eds.), *Struggles over difference: Curriculum, texts, and pedagogy in the Asia-Pacific*. Albany, NY: State University of New York Press.
36. Petty, R. & Cacioppo (1986), *Communication and Persuasion: Central and Peripheral Routes to Attitude Change*. New York: Springer Verlag.
37. Reagan, T.G., & T.A.Osborn. 2002. *The Foreign Language Educator in Society*. Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum.
38. Richards, J. C., & Rodgers, T. S. (2001). *Approaches and methods in language teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
39. Romaine, S. 2000. *Language in Society: An Introduction to Sociolinguistics*. 2nd ed. Oxford & New York: Oxford University Press
40. Sampson, G.P. (1984), 'Exporting Language Teaching Methods from Canada to China', *TESL Canada Journal*, vol. 1, no. 1.

41. Saville Troike, M. (1996), 'The Ethnography of Communication', in *Sociolinguistics and Language Teaching*, ed. S. L. McKay & N. L. Hornberger. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
42. Shardakova, M. & Pavlenko, A. (2004). Identity options in Russian textbooks. *Journal of Language, Identity, and Education*, 3(1), 25-46.
43. Shan, N. (2012). Russian language in China. *Journal of Russian Language in Education*, 9, 86-89.
44. Swan, M. (1995). *Practical English usage*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
45. Sperber, D. & Wilson, D. (1986) *Relevance: Communication and Cognition*. Oxford: Basil Blackwell.
46. Tang, L.X., n.d. [1983?], *TEFL in China: Methods and Techniques*. Shanghai: Shanghai Foreign Language Education Press.
47. Tsang, M. C. (2000). Education and national development in China since 1949: Oscillating policies and enduring dilemmas. *China Review*, 579-618.
48. Urban, G. (1971), *The Miracles of Chairman Mao: a Compendium of Devotional Literature 1966-1970*. London: Tom Stacey Ltd.
49. Van Dijk, T. A. (1993). Principles of critical discourse analysis. *Discourse & Society*, 4(2), 249-283.
50. White, G. (1976), *The Politics of Class and Class Origin: The Case of the Cultural Revolution*. Contemporary China Papers No. 9. Canberra: Contemporary China Centre, Australian National University.
51. Widdowson, H.G. (1990), *Aspects of Language Teaching*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. Brunnbauer, U. (2008). Making Bulgarians socialist: The fatherland front in Communist Bulgaria, 1944-1989. *East European Politics & Societies*, 22(1), 44-79.
52. Wodak (Ed.), *Language, power and ideology: studies in political discourse* (pp. 3-39). Amsterdam/Philadelphia: John Benjamins.
53. Wang Fuxia. *Zhongguo de Eyu Jiaoxue // Waiyu Jiaoxue yu Yanjiu*. – 1987. – No.2. (Ван Фуся. *Русский язык в Китае // Обучение и исследование иностранных языков*. – 1987. – № 2.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).